

H2020 – NMBP – EEB – 2019 – GA 869898

Highly advanced modular integration of insulation, energising and storage systems for non-residential buildings

D9.1 Project website

WP9 Dissemination, communication and exploitation

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Reviewed and approved by	Consortium steering committee	16.12.2019

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 869898

Distribution list

External		Internal	
European Commission	1x	Consortium partners	1x

Change log

Issue	Date	Pages	Remark / changes	Pages
0.1	09.12.2019	17	First issue by FENIX	All
0.2	09.12.2019	17	WP leader review by FENIX	All
1.0	16.12.2019	17	Approved final version by the steering committee	All

To be cited as

FENIX (2019): "D9.1 - Project website" of the HORIZON 2020 project POWERSKIN+. EC Grant Agreement No. 869898, Brno, Czech Republic.

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Terms, definitions and abbreviated terms

RP	Report
D	Deliverable
T	Task
WP	Work Package
KPI	Key Performance Indicator

1. Publishable summary

The deliverable D9.1 project website is a public document of the POWERSKIN+ project, delivered in the context of WP9 Dissemination, communication and exploitation, task T9.1 Communication and dissemination. This document presents the first step in the partial objective of developing and deploying a Communication and dissemination plan: the POWERSKIN+ project website, dedicated to the wide public audience all around the world. The website is not intended to be static. Especially the “News & Events”, “Gallery”, and “Documents” section will be once a month (or whenever needed) updated and managed by the Dissemination leader - FENIX based on the partners’ inputs and project’s development.

2. Executive summary

The deliverable D9.1 project website is a public document of the POWERSKIN+ project, delivered in the context of WP9 Dissemination, communication and exploitation, task T9.1 Communication and dissemination. The objective of task T9.1 is to secure the successful communication and dissemination through the implementation and deployment of a Communication and dissemination plan.

This document presents the first step in the partial objective of developing and deploying a Communication and dissemination plan: the POWERSKIN+ project website, dedicated to the wide public audience all around the world. As a first step, the logo of the project, dictating the visual identity, was developed. Once that was ready, an entire project website was constructed utilizing the visual identity. The website is available online and can be accessed at www.powerskinplus.eu.

The website is not intended to be static. Especially the “News & Events”, “Gallery”, and “Documents” section will be once a month (or whenever needed) updated and managed by the Dissemination leader - FENIX based on the partners’ inputs and project’s development. The design of the project website is planned to be updated minimum three times per project, reflecting the project’s main achievements, technical development, new videos, etc.. Different audiences are being considered and the information while technical and complete, it has been streamlined and presented in a way that is accessible by wide range of stakeholders. An initial version of POWERSKIN+ project website has been designed, provisioned and deployed on the internet at month M3. The site is hosted by FENIX – WP9 leader, under the domain powerskinplus.eu.

Google Analytics as Key Performance Indicator (KPI) has been considered and deployed at this early stage of the project (e.g. views, users, countries, languages, browsers, device, etc.). Another KPI which will be tracked is the downloads from the project website (e.g. promo materials, deliverables, publications, newsletters, etc.). The website was designed considering display on different devices such as desktop, mobile or tablet.

4. Project identity and public image

Visual and graphic point of view allows an easier identification for the public as well as an improved visibility to obtain a brand for the POWERSKIN+ project during the dissemination activities.

POWERSKIN+ logo was created by IPN already at the proposal stage in order to define a project identity, so clearly to identify any kind of internal or public document. Project logo can be used in the following cases:

- in all documents developed under the framework of the POWERSKIN+ project; in documents to be submitted to the EC (e.g. deliverables)
- in PowerPoint presentations to be used for communication and dissemination activities to be carried out by each participant under the framework of the project; in all promo material
- in POWERSKIN+ website, and in websites of the Participants with a link to the project website

Logo manual was developed in order to help partners correctly use the logo. POWERSKIN+ logo must be positioned in its own clear space away from design elements such as text and images.

Logo and logo manual download: <https://www.powerskinplus.eu/documents/promo-materials/logos>

FIGURE 1: POWERSKIN+ LOGO AND ITS APPLICATIONS

5. Website design and registration data

The POWERSKIN+ project website has been created during the early project stage and launched at month M3 under the www.powerskinplus.eu. Webhosting and domain were bought by FENIX in WEDOS provider. For the website, the following programming languages were used: html, php, database MySQL, JavaScript and reduction system based on the Open Source. Under the Webhosting project info email “info@powerskinplus.eu” was created to be further used for social network profiles registration, newsletter campaign, etc. Email is maintained by FENIX.

6. Website description

The website has been designed by FENIX and the main aim is to quickly address the key questions that external visitors to the website are expected to have:

- What is the project about?
- Who is participating in the project?
- What additional details are available?
- Who to contact for more information?

The website itself contains the following information:

- general information about the project and demo sites,
- partners' details,
- list of news and events,
- all public material that is generated by the project,
- links to social network profiles, twitter feed online,
- newsletter subscription,
- contact information,
- videos and gallery.

6.1 Home

The “Home” page of the POWERSKIN+ website contains basic information about the project. The upper part of the screen shows a navigation panel, using a structure that is commonly used. At the top of the page the project’s logo is placed, at the bottom of the page are shown short news, online twitter feed, links for the social profiles, contact, newsletter subscription, project identifiers and EU funding.

A short video clip introducing the POWERSKIN+ project was created by FENIX at month M3 and implemented in the Home page, as shown in Figure 1.

FIGURE 2: POWERSKIN+ HOME PAGE

Highly advanced modular integration of insulation, energizing & storage systems for non-residential buildings

INNOVATIVE FAÇADE SOLUTION

- + INSULATION & CLIMATE CONTROL
- + EASY MODULE INSTALLATION
- + ENERGY HARVESTING
- + ENERGY STORAGE

Concept

Taking advantage of its modular nature, different combinations of POWERSKIN+ modules and addons can be set to match any specific refurbishment need.

Concept

Partners

Demoversions

POWERSKIN+ façade renovation system will be demonstrated in 3 real-size non-residential buildings

Project roadmap

- Start: October 2019
- Sep 2021: Energy materials and integrated systems production, opaque and transparent prototype module
- Mar 2022: System add-on prototypes
- Mar 2023: Prototype system integration and validation
- Sep 2023: Demonstration in operational environment
- End: September 2023

Don't forget to **LIKE COMMENT & SUBSCRIBE**

The project leading to this application has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No. 869898.

FIGURE 3: POWERSKIN+ VIDEO CLIP

6.2 About

The “About” section presents the overall project concept and technology in detail.

FIGURE 4: POWERSKIN+ ABOUT SECTION

6.3 Demo sites

The “Demo sites” section is dedicated to POWERSKIN+ demos in Portugal, Czech Republic and Slovenia. More information will be added based on the project’s technical development.

FIGURE 5: POWERSKIN+ DEMO SITES SECTION

6.4 News & Events

This page presents a list of news and events, which will include all meetings of the project partners and important events in which a large group of the consortium partners participates, such as conferences, fairs, workshops, etc. Short info about the most relevant upcoming news is reflected at the bottom part of the website in Home page.

FIGURE 6: POWERSKIN+ NEWS & EVENTS SECTION

6.5 Gallery

Gallery section displays images from meetings, events and shows pictures related to the project. In this section, individual albums are possible to be created for easier viewing and photo organization.

FIGURE 7: POWERSKIN+ GALLERY SECTION

6.6 Videos

In this section, various videos created for the POWERSKIN+ project will be stored and available to the public (in addition to the YouTube channel).

FIGURE 8: POWERSKIN+ VIDEOS SECTION

6.7 Documents

The “Documents” section is split into subsections Deliverables, Promo-material (subsections: Logos, Press Releases, Newsletters, Leaflets, Posters, Presentations), Publications (subsections: Scientific Publications, Popularized publications), Meetings and events, Clustering activities and Other. Subsections can be added based on the project requirements at any time. The Documents page will contain all material that has been published and is thus publicly available (respecting copyright issues).

FIGURE 9: POWERSKIN+ DOCUMENTS SECTION

6.8 Partners

This part of the website contains information about the partners involved in the POWERSKIN+ project. It shows each partner’s name, logo and a link to the partner’s homepage. This part of the website will be static, except for the case of a partner change in the project or logo change.

FIGURE 10: POWERSKIN+ PARTNERS SECTION

6.9 Contact

The last part of the project website contains the contact information of the coordinator. It is intended for any inquiries by interested parties.

FIGURE 11: POWERSKIN+ CONTACT SECTION

6.10 Social media and newsletter subscription

Within the social media campaign, social network profiles were created and linked to the project website. Social profiles used from month M1 and updated weekly are: LinkedIn, Facebook, Instagram and Twitter. The project website also contains an online Twitter feed.

FIGURE 12: POWERSKIN+ SOCIAL NETWORK PROFILES

Newsletter subscription is linked to the info@powerskinplus.eu where all subscribers are collected for Newsletter campaign following the GDPR policy.

FIGURE 13: POWERSKIN+ SOCIAL NETWORK PROFILES LINKS AND NEWSLETTER SUBSCRIPTION

6.11 Cookies

Cookies are small text files stored on users' computer by their browser. They have many applications, such as: tracking users as they navigate around a website; remembering user preferences; auto-logins for visitors coming back to a site; and website security. Within POWERSKIN+ project website cookies policy was also implemented.

6.12 Future work

Short term improvements to the website under consideration at the time of deliverable writing include:

- update of the website content based on the project progress annually
- translation into partners' languages to overcome the language barrier in case consortium partners are interested
- adding cluster projects page in order to increase the visibility of such projects and initiate the cooperation
- in case of workshop organization by project or together with cluster projects, registration page and event info to be created

7. Conclusion

The online POWERSKIN+ website is a key element of the project's dissemination and communication strategy. This site will ensure the visibility of the project, facilitate the diffusion of the project's results and promote their exploitation.

An initial version of the POWERSKIN+ project website has been designed, provisioned and deployed on the internet at month M3. Consisting mostly of static content, it has been designed to quickly answer the key questions that external visitors to the website are expected to have. The project website will continuously form and develop as the project itself grows.

The information included on the project website is likely to be valuable even after the project has finished. Therefore, the consortium aims at ensuring that the website will continue to exist after the project funding has finished min 2 years and that bookmarks and published URLs will continue to function.

